

HISTORY OF THE EMERGENCE OF PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract. This study discusses the emergence of the science of pedagogical psychology and the role of scientists from around the world and our country in the development of the science of pedagogical psychology.

Keywords: heterogeneity, heterochrony, pedagogical science, pedagogical knowledge, intelligence, pragmatic functional psychology, trial and error theory, programming education practice.

PEDAGOGIK PSIXOLOGIYANING YUZAGA KELISH TARIXI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda pedagogik psixologiya fanining paydo bo'lishi, jahon va yurtimizning olimlarining pedagogik psixologiya fani rivojida qo'shgan o'rni haqida mulohaza yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: heterojenlik, geteroxroniya, pedagogika fani, pedagogik bilish, intellekt, Pragmatik funksional psixologiya, Sinov va xato nazariyasi, dasturiy ta'lim amaliyoti.

ИСТОРИЯ ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЯ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ПСИХОЛОГИИ

Аннотация. В данной работе рассматривается становление науки педагогической психологии и роль ученых всего мира и нашей страны в развитии науки педагогической психологии.

Ключевые слова: гетерогенность, гетерохронность, педагогическая наука, педагогические знания, интеллект, прагматическая функциональная психология, теория проб и ошибок, практика программирования.

Introduction

The development of many branches of scientific knowledge is a heterogeneous and heterochronic process, moreover, a process torn apart in time. This is usually explained by major socio-historical events (revolutions, wars, natural disasters) occurring in the world, which significantly affect the content and direction of scientific development. However, once it has arisen, it continues due to the unstoppable movement of human thought itself. Pedagogical thought, first set forth in the work of Jan Amos Komensky "Great Didactics" in 1657, laid the foundation for the development of pedagogical theory and the purposeful organization of school education. This work can also be considered as the first prerequisite for the long, contradictory development of educational psychology over more than 250 years, since it began to take shape as an independent science only at the end of the 19th century. The entire path of the formation and development of pedagogical science can be represented by three large periods (stages).

Despite the fact that pedagogical psychology emerged as a separate subject at the beginning of the 19th century, its development as an independent science and the path to its establishment were quite complicated. The constant struggle between different worldviews had a great influence on the development of this science. Depending on which worldview prevailed at a particular stage of the historical development of society, the level and quality of research, how to interpret the results obtained, were determined. Although in the past our ancestors did not study the psychological laws of man consistently, comprehensively, in a specific scientific direction, the manifestation of these phenomena in the manuscripts of scientists, their valuable thoughts about human development, are still of great importance.

Abu Nasr Al-Farabi, in the positive solution of pedagogical issues and the psychological and physiological problems associated with them, says that a person consists of parts that are integral and interconnected in every way. Al-Farabi considers the role of science in the knowledge of existence to be a decisive factor. In his opinion, the human body, brain, sensory organs are present at birth, but mental knowledge, spirituality, spirit, intellectual and moral qualities, character, religion, customs, education arise in communication with the external environment, other people, etc., a person acquires them and achieves them with the help of his activity. It is emphasized that his mind is the most mature product of his thought, spiritual growth.

Abu Rayhan Al-Biruni's thoughts on the purpose, tasks and position of education and upbringing, the development of man and the younger generation were truly created on the basis of humanism and anthropology. The principles of harmony of knowledge and upbringing with nature can be observed in all the works of the thinker. He emphasizes that man is a part of nature.

Biruni, having delved deeply into the nature of the educational process and built on the basis of taking into account the age characteristics of children, teaches harmony with nature.

In Biruni's pedagogical work, the main issue was man and his happiness, education, and perfection.

The valuable information of Abu Ali ibn Sina, a wise man and a genius of medicine who lived and worked in the Middle Ages, about the human psyche, the unity of the mind and the heart, the structure of the human body, its nervous activity and their branching and states, still forms an important basis of medicine.

One of the main issues of Yusuf Khos Hajib is the upbringing of a perfect person. In his works, the writer consistently expresses his principles on the basis of how he imagined the most perfect person, able to meet the requirements of society at that time. The work "Qudadgu Bilig" ("Guide to Happiness") is a spiritual source on morality and etiquette, embodying the methods, measures and guidelines of education and upbringing, spiritual perfection.

Abdurakhmon Jomi's "Bahoristan", "Khirandnomai Iskandari", "Tuhtaful Ahror" and other works express his thoughts on science and enlightenment, education and upbringing, professional and craft study, and positive human qualities.

Alisher Navoi's "Khazoyinul Maoniy", "Mahbubul Qulub" and other works contain valuable reflections on the morality, spirituality, attitude towards others, talents and abilities of a mature and harmonious person. It is emphasized that these psychological criteria are important for establishing social justice.

Also, in Navoi's works, the role of parents in the formation of the younger generation as a well-rounded person, the chastity of women, and the modesty of men occupy a special place. Empirical data from experiments by G. Ebbinghaus (1885) on the study of the forgetting process and the forgetting curve obtained by him, the nature of which is taken into account by all subsequent researchers of memory, skill development, and organization of exercises. Pragmatic functional psychology of W. James (late 19th - early 20th centuries) and J. Dewey (virtually the entire first half of our century) with an emphasis on adaptive reactions, adaptation to the environment, organism activity, and skill development. Trial and error theory of E. Thorndike (late 19th - early 20th centuries), who formulated the basic laws of learning - the laws of exercise, effect, and readiness; who described the learning curve and achievement tests based on this data (1904). Behaviorism of J. Watson (1912-1920) and neobehaviorism of E. Tolman, K. Hull, A. Gasri, and B. Skinner (first half of our century). B. Skinner already in the middle of our century developed the concept of operant behavior and the practice of programmed learning. The merit of the works of E. Thorndike preceding behaviorism, the orthodox behaviorism of J. Watson and the entire neo-behaviorist trend is the development of a holistic concept of learning, including its patterns, facts, mechanisms.

Conclusion

The future begins today. If we do not pay attention to the issue of education now, the future will be lost. Spiritual and moral purification, faith, honesty, piety, honor, kindness and similar truly human qualities do not come by themselves. Education is the basis of everything. It is teachers who carry out the work of raising a fully mature and harmonious generation and educating them.

Therefore, it is appropriate for future psychologists and current students of pedagogical universities to have a deep knowledge of developmental psychology and pedagogical psychology.

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